

Ravulizumab in atypical hemolytic-uremic syndrome: a case report in a young woman with renal failure

Georgi Nikolov^{1,2}, Dimitar Nikolov^{1,2},
 Maria-Florance Kitova⁴, Anna A. Mihaylova⁵

1 Department of Nephrology, Faculty of Medicine, Medical University of Plovdiv, Plovdiv, Bulgaria

2 St George University Hospital, Plovdiv, Bulgaria

3 Section of Cardiology, First Department of Internal Diseases, Faculty of Medicine, Medical University of Plovdiv, Plovdiv, Bulgaria

4 Faculty of Medicine, Medical University of Plovdiv, Plovdiv, Bulgaria

5 Department of Health Care Management, Faculty of Public Health, Medical University of Plovdiv, Plovdiv, Bulgaria

6 Research Institute at Medical University of Plovdiv, Medical University of Plovdiv, Plovdiv, Bulgaria

Corresponding author: Anna A. Mihaylova (anna.mihaylova@mu-plovdiv.bg)

Received 25 January 2026 ♦ Accepted 14 May 2026 ♦ Published 4 June 2026

Citation: Nikolov G, Nikolov D, Zheleva V, Kitov S, Kitova M-F, Mihaylova AA, Kitova L (2026) Ravulizumab in atypical hemolytic-uremic syndrome: a case report in a young woman with renal failure. *Pharmacia* 73: e186371. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e186371>

Abstract

Atypical hemolytic-uremic syndrome (aHUS) is a rare, life-threatening, complement-mediated thrombotic microangiopathy characterized by microangiopathic hemolytic anemia, thrombocytopenia, and acute kidney injury. Delayed diagnosis and treatment are associated with a high risk of irreversible renal damage and progression to end-stage kidney disease.

This report describes the case of a 35-year-old woman who presented with severe thrombotic microangiopathy and rapidly progressive renal failure requiring dialysis. A systematic diagnostic approach enabled the exclusion of thrombotic thrombocytopenic purpura, Shiga toxin-associated hemolytic-uremic syndrome, and secondary causes of thrombotic microangiopathy, leading to a diagnosis of aHUS. Targeted complement inhibition with the long-acting C5 inhibitor ravulizumab was initiated early in the disease course. Treatment resulted in rapid hematologic stabilization, resolution of hemolysis, and partial recovery of renal function.

This case illustrates the importance of prompt recognition of aHUS and early initiation of mechanism-based therapy. Ravulizumab represents an effective targeted pharmacological option in severe aHUS, including cases with advanced renal involvement, and may substantially improve hematologic and renal outcomes when applied in accordance with international guidelines.

Keywords

atypical hemolytic-uremic syndrome, complement inhibition, ravulizumab, renal involvement, thrombotic microangiopathy

Introduction

Atypical hemolytic-uremic syndrome (aHUS) is a rare, life-threatening disorder belonging to the group of

thrombotic microangiopathies (TMA), characterized by the triad of microangiopathic hemolytic anemia, thrombocytopenia, and acute kidney injury (Noris and Remuzzi 2009; Loirat and Frémeaux-Bacchi 2011; Fakhouri et al.

2013). Unlike typical Shiga toxin-associated HUS, aHUS results from chronic dysregulation of the alternative complement pathway, most commonly due to genetic or acquired defects in complement regulatory mechanisms (Noris and Remuzzi 2009; Fakhouri et al. 2013).

Uncontrolled complement activation leads to persistent endothelial injury, microvascular thrombosis, and progressive organ damage, with the kidneys being the most frequently and severely affected organs. In the absence of timely treatment, up to 50–60% of patients develop end-stage kidney disease during the first disease episode (Noris and Remuzzi 2009; Loirat and Frémeaux-Bacchi 2011; Fakhouri et al. 2013).

The diagnosis of aHUS is one of exclusion and requires systematic differentiation from other forms of TMA in accordance with international recommendations (KDIGO Glomerular Diseases Work Group 2021; Tektonidou et al. 2020). The introduction of C5 inhibitors has profoundly altered the natural history of the disease, with optimal therapeutic benefit being closely associated with early treatment initiation (Fakhouri et al. 2013; Rondeau et al. 2019).

The diagnostic process remains a major clinical challenge, as aHUS must be distinguished from thrombotic thrombocytopenic purpura, typical HUS, and secondary TMAs associated with autoimmune, infectious, neoplastic, or drug-related causes. International guidelines emphasize that diagnostic and therapeutic delay is a key determinant of poor outcome.

The introduction of targeted therapy with C5 inhibitors, such as eculizumab and the newer long-acting ravulizumab, has significantly improved survival and renal outcomes. However, the therapeutic effect is strongly

dependent on early complement inhibition, underscoring the importance of timely disease recognition.

In this context, a clinical case is presented of a young woman with severe aHUS resulting in dialysis dependence, in whom treatment with ravulizumab led to hematologic stabilization and partial renal recovery. The case highlights the diagnostic and therapeutic challenges of aHUS and underscores the importance of applying international recommendations in real-world clinical practice.

Case presentation, clinical data, medical history

The patient is a 35-year-old woman with a history of arterial hypertension diagnosed approximately 7–8 months prior to the current illness, with poor blood pressure control despite antihypertensive therapy. She also reported long-standing anemia of approximately 10–12 years' duration, repeatedly treated with oral iron preparations (iron salts and combined iron-folate formulations), with only a transient and incomplete response, without a clearly established etiology.

The current illness had an acute onset over several days with generalized weakness, marked fatigue, nausea, and recurrent vomiting, without diarrhea. Simultaneously, the patient noted a progressive decrease in urine output leading to oligoanuria, as well as lumbar discomfort and pain, more pronounced on the left side. During this period, worsening blood pressure control was observed, with values up to 160/100 mmHg and subsequent hypertensive peaks. The pathophysiological mechanisms of aHUS and the role of complement inhibition are summarized in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Pathophysiology of atypical hemolytic-uremic syndrome (aHUS)—dysregulation of the alternative complement pathway and the role of C5 inhibitors. Adapted from data by Noris and Remuzzi (2009), Loirat and Frémeaux-Bacchi (2011), Fakhouri et al. (2013), KDIGO (2021), Tektonidou et al. (2020), Rondeau et al. (2019), and Kulasekararaj et al. (2019).

Due to symptom progression, the patient sought emergency medical care. Laboratory tests revealed severe anemia, thrombocytopenia, and markedly elevated nitrogenous waste products, prompting hospitalization. During the initial hospital stay, rapid progression of renal failure, worsening anemia, and oligoanuria were observed, leading to referral to a specialized nephrology center.

The patient reported a prior episode of pyelonephritis approximately 2 years earlier without chronic sequelae and vertebroplasty for Th12 and L1 fractures 1 year before the current illness, at which time renal function was normal. She also had a history of bronchial asthma without recent exacerbations. She denied preceding diarrhea, infections, pregnancy, exposure to nephrotoxic drugs, or a family history of renal or hematologic diseases.

The clinical course, in combination with rapidly progressive renal failure and laboratory evidence of hemolysis, suggested an acute episode of thrombotic microangiopathy, prompting further diagnostic and therapeutic evaluation. The dynamics of the main laboratory parameters are presented in Table 1. The results of the immunological and infectious investigations are summarized in Table 2.

Laboratory and instrumental findings

Imaging

Renal ultrasonography demonstrated bilaterally reduced kidneys with hyperechogenic parenchyma and no evidence of obstruction.

Diagnostic considerations

The classical triad of microangiopathic hemolytic anemia, thrombocytopenia, and acute kidney injury fulfilled the definition of TMA according to KDIGO guidelines (KDIGO Glomerular Diseases Work Group 2021). Systematic exclusion of thrombotic thrombocytopenic purpura, typical HUS, and secondary TMAs is a mandatory diagnostic

Table 1. Dynamics of main laboratory parameters.

Parameter	Reference range	Minimum value	Maximum value
Hemoglobin (g/L)	120–160	55	121
Platelets ($\times 10^9/L$)	150–400	49	145
LDH (U/L)	<250	684	4363
Haptoglobin (g/L)	0.3–2.0	0.02	0.04
Creatinine ($\mu\text{mol/L}$)	<90	406	856
eGFR (ml/min/1.73 m^2)	>90	<15	<15
Proteinuria (g/24h)	<0.15	0.37	10.6

Table 2. Immunological and infectious investigations.

Test	Result
ANA, anti-dsDNA	Negative
ANCA	Negative
Antiphospholipid antibodies	Negative
C3 / C4	Low-normal
HBV, HCV, HIV	Negative
ADAMTS13 activity	Within normal limits (ref. range: > 50% (severe deficiency < 10%))

step according to European League Against Rheumatism (EULAR) recommendations (Tektonidou et al. 2020; KDIGO Glomerular Diseases Work Group 2021).

ADAMTS13 activity was within the normal range (reference range: >50%; severe deficiency defined as <10%), thereby excluding severe ADAMTS13 deficiency and making thrombotic thrombocytopenic purpura unlikely (Noris and Remuzzi 2009; KDIGO Glomerular Diseases Work Group 2021). The predominant renal involvement further supported this interpretation. The absence of diarrheal illness or an infectious trigger argued against Shiga toxin-associated HUS (Loirat and Frémeaux-Bacchi 2011). After exclusion of secondary causes, a diagnosis of aHUS was considered most likely, in full accordance with EULAR recommendations (Tektonidou et al. 2020). The hematologic and renal response following initiation of anti-complement therapy is illustrated in Fig. 2. The diagnostic approach used for differentiation of thrombotic microangiopathy is summarized in Fig. 3.

Figure 2. Dynamics of hemoglobin, platelet count, and serum creatinine over time relative to the initiation of anti-complement therapy.

Figure 3. Diagnostic algorithm for thrombotic microangiopathy: stepwise differentiation of TTP, typical HUS, secondary TMA, and aHUS.

Treatment

Therapeutic management focused on controlling the life-threatening acute condition, stabilizing hemodynamics, suppressing hemolysis, and limiting the progression of renal damage. Treatment included supportive care, kidney replacement therapy, and targeted anti-complement therapy.

Supportive and symptomatic treatment

Initial management included correction of fluid and electrolyte imbalance due to oligoanuria and risk of hypervolemia; blood pressure control using combined antihypertensive therapy (ACE inhibitor/ARB, calcium channel blocker, and alpha-blocker); prophylactic anticoagulation with low-molecular-weight heparin on non-dialysis days, with close platelet monitoring; and gastroprotection and corticosteroids during the early diagnostic phase. Red blood cell transfusions were administered restrictively and only when clinically indicated.

Kidney replacement therapy

Due to rapid progression to oligoanuric renal failure and uremic syndrome, intermittent hemodialysis was initiated via a central venous catheter (PermCath) with 3 h sessions and individualized ultrafiltration volumes under hemodynamically stable conditions.

Anti-complement therapy with ravulizumab

According to KDIGO and EULAR guidelines, treatment with a C5 inhibitor should be initiated imme-

diately in cases of confirmed TMA with severe organ involvement, without awaiting genetic or histological confirmation (Tektonidou et al. 2020; KDIGO Glomerular Diseases Work Group 2021). Ravulizumab, a long-acting monoclonal antibody against C5, was administered. It blocks the formation of the membrane attack complex and interrupts the key pathogenic mechanism in aHUS (Fakhouri et al. 2013; Schrezenmeier et al. 2020). Clinical studies have demonstrated rapid suppression of hemolysis, platelet normalization, and significant improvement in renal function with C5 inhibition (Fakhouri et al. 2013; Rondeau et al. 2019; Schrezenmeier et al. 2020). Dosing regimen: loading dose of 3000 mg intravenously, adjusted to body weight, followed by maintenance dosing at extended intervals according to approved protocols.

Mechanism of action: Ravulizumab prevents cleavage of C5 into C5a and C5b, thereby inhibiting C5b-9 formation, leading to interruption of complement-mediated endothelial injury, suppression of microangiopathic thrombosis, and rapid control of hemolysis (Kulasekararaj et al. 2019; Schrezenmeier et al. 2020).

1. Treatment response

After initiation of anti-complement therapy:

- Hematologic stabilization was observed, with rising hemoglobin, platelet normalization, and progressive LDH reduction;
- Hemolytic activity resolved without recurrent TMA episodes;

- Partial recovery of renal function occurred, although advanced chronic kidney disease persisted, likely due to delayed treatment initiation.

2. Safety and follow-up

Anti-complement therapy was well tolerated, with no infusion reactions or infectious complications during hospitalization. The patient was discharged with recommendations for long-term nephrology follow-up, monitoring of hematologic and renal parameters, continuation of supportive therapy, and surveillance for infections associated with complement blockade.

Therapeutic conclusion

This case demonstrates that anti-complement therapy with ravulizumab is the key pathogenetically targeted treatment for aHUS. Early initiation is critical for optimal hematologic and renal outcomes. Treatment delay likely contributed to advanced chronic kidney damage.

Outcome and follow-up

After therapy initiation, hemolytic activity stabilized, platelet counts increased, LDH levels markedly decreased, and partial renal recovery was achieved.

Discussion

This case illustrates a typical but severe presentation of aHUS in an adult patient, characterized by acute onset, rapid progression of TMA, and predominant renal involvement (Noris and Remuzzi 2009; Loirat and Frémeaux-Bacchi 2011). As reported in cohort studies and registries, delayed diagnosis and advanced organ damage at presentation are key predictors of poor renal outcome. Nevertheless, even in dialysis-dependent patients, initiation of targeted anti-complement therapy can alter the disease trajectory.

Accumulating evidence indicates that early C5 inhibition is associated with superior hematologic and renal outcomes, including higher rates of dialysis independence and reduced progression to end-stage kidney disease (Fakhouri et al. 2013; Rondeau et al. 2019; Schrezenmeier et al. 2020). This case supports current international recommendations emphasizing early diagnosis and prompt initiation of complement inhibition in suspected aHUS to optimize outcomes and limit irreversible kidney damage (Tektonidou et al. 2020; KDIGO Glomerular Diseases Work Group 2021).

Conclusion

aHUS requires a high index of clinical suspicion. A systematic diagnostic approach and early initiation of

complement-inhibiting therapy in accordance with KDIGO and EULAR guidelines are decisive for prognosis (Rondeau et al. 2019; Tektonidou et al. 2020; KDIGO Glomerular Diseases Work Group 2021).

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for publication of this case report and accompanying anonymized clinical data. Patient confidentiality and privacy were fully protected in accordance with ethical standards and the Declaration of Helsinki.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

Regarding the use of AI in the preparation of this manuscript, the authors declare the following:

Artificial intelligence-based tool ChatGPT 5,2 were used solely for the preparation and visualization of figures. AI was not used in data analysis, interpretation, or manuscript writing.

Funding

No funding was reported.

Author contributions

D.N.: conceptualization of the study, patient management, manuscript drafting, and critical revisions; G.N. and V.Z.: literature review, data collection, and interpretation of clinical findings; M.F.K.: preparation of tables and discussion section; S.K.: diagnostic data analysis, evaluation, and clinical correlation; A.M.: pharma cological review and contribution to manuscript editing; L.K.: supervision, final approval of the manuscript, and overall coordination of the study. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Author ORCIDs

Dimitar Nikolov <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7503-119X>

Violeta Zheleva <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2273-5919>

Spas Kitov <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1138-2844>

Anna A. Mihaylova <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7674-6074>

Lyudmila Kitova <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3767-9972>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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